

COMPARATIVE THE EFFECTIVENESS OF CONSTRUCTIVISM AND META LEARNING ON STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AND RETENTION IN FINANCIAL ACCOUNTING IN UNIVERSITIES IN ENUGU STATE

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Abstract

The study compared the effectiveness of constructivism and meta-learning on students' academic achievement and retention in financial accounting in universities in Enugu State. Four research questions guided the study. Four null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted a quasi-experimental design of pre-test, post-test, non-equivalent control group design. Intact classes were used and there was no randomization of the research subjects into control and experimental groups. The study was conducted in universities in Enugu State. The target population for the study comprised 123 year four accounting education students in the universities in Enugu State. There was no sampling due to manageable size of the population. The first instrument, Financial Accounting Achievement Test I (FAAT I) otherwise known as pre-test was administered to students in order to determine their entry level. The second instrument, Financial Accounting Achievement Test II (FAAT II) otherwise known as Post-test was used to determine the academic achievement scores of students after treatment. Lastly, Financial Accounting Achievement Test III (FAAT III) a reshuffled of FAAT II was used to test retention ability of students after two weeks of treatment. The instrument for data collection were validated by three research experts, two from Department of Business and Entrepreneurship Education and one expert in Measurement and Evaluation unit of Mathematics and Computer Education. The research experts are from Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT). A reliability coefficient of 0.80 was obtained using Kuder-Richardson formula 20 (K-R-20). The research questions were answered using mean with standard deviation. The hypotheses for the study were tested using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at 0.05 level of significance. A null hypothesis of no significant difference was upheld when the p-value reached a significance level that was greater than or equal to 0.05. On the other hand, the null hypothesis of no significant difference was not upheld when the p-value was less than 0.05. Results from the findings showed that constructivist teaching method is more effective than meta-learning teaching method in improving academic achievement of year 4 students in Financial Accounting. In addition, constructivist teaching method also happens to be more effective for enhancing retention ability of students in Financial Accounting than meta-learning method. It was recommended among others that since the use of constructivist method enhance academic achievement of students in financial accounting in universities, the lecturers in universities in Enugu State should adopt the use of this method for instructional delivery. This should come as the new policy of government to be integrated in the curriculum.

Keywords: Comparative, Effectiveness, Constructivism, Meta-learning, Students, Academic Achievement, Retention, Financial Accounting

Introduction

Universities serve as vital pillars of society, shaping future professionals, nurturing critical thinking and research capabilities, and driving innovation across diverse disciplines. As defined by Ogunode (2020), a university is a higher education institution that offers a broad spectrum of academic programs and degrees across various fields. These institutions typically comprise multiple Colleges or Faculties, each dedicated to specific areas such as arts and humanities, education, sciences, social sciences, business, law, medicine, and engineering. Universities generally operate with a degree of autonomy, allowing them to establish their own academic standards and policies. Governance is often overseen by a Board of Trustees or a council. Public universities, according to Ogunode and Abubakar (2020), are government-owned institutions created to provide post-secondary education to the populace. In Nigeria, these public universities are categorized into federal and state institutions, federal universities are managed by the federal government, while state universities fall under the jurisdiction of individual state governments (Suleiman, 2022). The objectives of Nigerian universities, as outlined by Suleiman (2022), include fostering value orientation essential for individual and societal survival, enhancing intellectual capacity to understand and engage with the environment, and equipping individuals with both physical and intellectual skills to become productive members of their communities. Additionally, they aim to cultivate a broad understanding of both local and global contexts (FGN, 2014). Financial accounting is one of the courses offered in the university.

Financial accounting is the systematic recording, interpretation, verification, and reporting of financial transactions in accordance with established accounting principles. Aydin (2020) defined Financial Accounting as a broad term encompassing both bookkeeping and accounting functions within any economic entity. According to Oyeyemi and Oyeyemi (2021), it involves capturing, processing, and communicating financial data. Umekwe (2023) emphasized that financial accounting serves as an information system, measuring and conveying economic activities to stakeholders for analysis and decision-making. Uwakwe and Okeke (2023) described financial accounting as the process of collecting, documenting, presenting, evaluating, and interpreting financial statements over time. The importance of financial accounting according to Olowodun and Egonu (2023), is to: (i) prepare students for careers in accounting fields; (ii) provide fundamental instructions that will help students assume their economic roles as consumers, workers, and citizens; (iii) to provide background instructions to assist students in preparing for other professional careers requiring advanced study in book-keeping and accounting skills for personal and future use. At the university level, financial accounting aims to equip students with practical skills and theoretical knowledge. The National Policy on Education (2013) outlines its objectives as follows: i. To provide vocational skills that enhance career prospects. ii. To develop proficiency in recording business transactions. iii. To foster understanding of business practices and procedures. iv. To train students in daily bookkeeping activities. v. To help students grasp the interrelated steps in the

accounting cycle. Achieving these goals requires effective learning methods that foster student engagement and comprehension, thereby enhancing students' academic achievement.

Academic achievement is the level of academic success obtained by students after undertaking an evaluation exercise in the classroom or laboratory. Sushma (2020) stated that academic achievement indicates the extent to which students have accomplished the specific instructional objectives of a subject matter in schools. It is the scholastic ranking of student's academic expertise on financial accounting. According to Bernido (2020), academic achievement refers to the successful result of interaction between a teacher and a student. It is designed to measure an individual's level of skill accomplishment or knowledge in a specific area. Academic achievement is appropriate in determining the efficacy of instruction and also useful in testing retention of information or skill. Bupo and Ibeneme (2024) noted that academic achievement is the extent to which a student has achieved the short-term goals of a course, measured in the scores obtained after a test. Bupo and Ibeneme further noted that achievement is in collaboration with retention.

Retention of learning is simply the ability to remember what has been learnt. Sushma (2020) stated that retention of learning is the ability to retain the knowledge of what is learnt and to be able to recall it when it is required. Also, psychomotor retention scores indicate the percentage or degree of originally learned skill that is remembered or recalled as a function of elapsed time. This implies that a learner who repeats an acquired piece of knowledge with less error is said to have retained the material learnt. Retention helps in knowledge development and knowledge development can be guaranteed when students are actively involved in teaching and learning processes (Chukwunta, 2024). The major problem faced by most students is inability to remember what they have learnt which could result to students performing poorly in achievement test. Retention in financial accounting is not acquired by observing the teacher demonstrate and mere memorization rather through student's participation rooted in appropriate teaching method.

To teach financial accounting effectively, educators must adopt instructional methods that resonate with both male and female students, stimulate interest, and promote high performance. Pradeep (2020) noted that the effect of instructional methods on students' achievement and retention knowledge can be influenced by the gender of a student. According to Aydin (2020), gender implies the character of being male or female, man or woman, boy or girl. Gender issues, as a factor or variable in this study, are not yet skewed to any direction. Bupo and Ibeneme (2020) reported a significant gender difference in the mean scores of students' academic performance in Financial Accounting in favour of female students while Abdulsalam (2022), Umar and Kankia (2024) established a gender disparity in the academic achievement and retention of students in Financial Accounting in favour of male students. The disparities between male and female students' achievement, interest and retention in Financial Accounting could be addressed effectively by the use of appropriate teaching methods.

Appropriate teaching methods are essential for preparing students for the workforce or further education in accounting. Methods that foster classroom engagement help students develop problem-solving skills and apply their knowledge to societal issues. Conversely, teacher-centered approaches, such as conventional lecture methods, may hinder student participation and limit academic success (Adaramola, 2020). Adaramola (2020) defined the lecture method as one where the teacher dominates the learning process. Abdulsalam (2022) noted that although it is the most widely used method among educators, it does not promote critical thinking, creativity, or problem-solving skills. Generally, scholars have agreed that when it comes to numerical subjects such as mathematics, statistics and element of finance among others, teacher's factor contributed most. Uwakwe and Okeke (2023) attributed the poor performance of students in numerical subjects such as accounting to the teaching approach adopted by teacher. Over reliance on these methods has been linked to poor academic performance, particularly among financial accounting students (Ilyas, Agus & Ahmad, 2021). In response, Ilyas, et al advocated for the adoption of student-centre learning methods that enhance effective learning such as constructivism, and meta-learning.

Constructivism teaching method is a learner-centered approach to instruction based on constructivism learning theory that says that all knowledge is constructed from a base of prior knowledge. Abiogu, Ugwu and Ede (2020) stated that constructivism is a teaching method with an approach that seeks opportunities for students to analyze, investigate, collaborate and share. In this method, students build and generate ideas based on what they already know rather than facts, skills and processes they can parrot. In other words, students construct their own understanding through the interactions of their existing experiences with whatever they come in contact. This makes learning a social activity which engages learners to questions, challenge and formulates their own ideas and conclusions (Ilyas, Agus & Ahmad, 2021). Jimoh (2021) noted that constructivism is a paradigm that hypothesizes learning as an active, contextualized, or constructive process. It is also a method by which instruction is mapped and organized to enable students to utilize their innately constructed ideas and thoughts to actively innovate knowledge that is meaningful to them. Apart from constructivism, meta-learning is another teaching method that is learner centered.

Meta-learning is a learner- centered approach to teaching and learning that trains the learners consciousness on the use of meta- cognitive processes for learning. It is a concept that describes the process of becoming a more effective learner. This knowledge is used to monitor and regulate cognitive processes such as reasoning, comprehension and problem-solving. In the learning classroom, Financial Accounting students can plan, execute, monitor and evaluate their learning activities. Eze, Ezenwafor and Obidile (2020) defined meta-learning as an instructional approach that emphasizes helping learners understand and control their own learning process. A teacher can encourage students to go "meta" in their learning by informing the students what the learning contents/experiences is all about, what the specific objectives are, what tools are to be used to motivate them and help to achieve the objectives.

Çelik (2022) opined that effective teaching and learning in classroom endorses active learning where students take control of their learning by recognizing when they understand and when they need more information. Çelik further observed that learners in meta-learning classroom are the most successful students in arts and science subjects because they set goals for their performance, plan how to use their time, focus their attention on the tasks and keep them motivated. This is an indication that when students are actively involved in the teaching and learning, it tends to facilitate mastery and retention which in turn improves their academic achievement.

At the university level, students are expected to acquire functional knowledge of financial accounting principles and apply these skills in real-world contexts. They are also encouraged to cultivate analytical attitudes, such as curiosity and precision, to address economic challenges during periods of recession. Despite its recognized importance, financial accounting instruction in Enugu State tertiary institutions has been largely ineffective (Chukwunta, 2024). Students consistently perform poorly in both internal and external assessments. Chukwunta (2024) noted poor students' achievement in financial accounting in both internal and standard examinations. Chukwunta further reported that the results approved by the Senate of the University of Nigeria and Enugu State University of Science and Technology revealed that 42.43 percent of the students who took Financial Accounting in 2024 scored below grade C. Chukwunta also noted that this poor achievement cannot be unconnected with the teaching methods adopted by the teachers. Evidence increasingly supports the notion that students achieve and retain more when they actively engage with lesson objectives and content ((Olowodun & Egonu, 2023; Chukwunta, 2024). This underscores the need for learner-centered strategies to effectively meet the goals of financial accounting education. Since mastering financial accounting requires deep theoretical understanding and practical application, passive learning through conventional methods is insufficient. Innovative approaches are essential to enhance academic performance and retention among university students. This study, therefore, sought to determine whether the use of constructivism and meta learning methods can improve students' achievement and retention in financial accounting, particularly in universities in Enugu State.

Statement of the Problem

Accounting, particularly financial accounting, is an essential component of virtually all business activities and is often referred to as the "language of business." In universities in Nigeria, financial accounting is included in the accounting curriculum to equip students with practical skills for both office-based employment and self-employment. At the university level, financial accounting aims to equip students with practical skills and theoretical knowledge. The course aims to prepare learners for careers in business and to help them fulfill their economic roles as consumers, workers, and responsible citizens. However, the intended goals of teaching financial accounting in Nigerian universities appear to be falling short. Many students struggle to grasp the necessary skills and navigate the complexities of the subject. This challenge is especially evident in Enugu State, where students performance in financial accounting

has been consistently poor. The results approved by the Senate of the University of Nigeria and Enugu State University of Science and Technology revealed that 42.43 percent of the students who took Financial Accounting in 2024 scored below grade C. This troubling trend has left many students graduating without marketable skills. A major contributing factor is the continued reliance on traditional teaching methods, primarily lectures and demonstrations, which dominate classroom instruction. Research indicates that these conventional approaches limit student engagement, thereby contribute to poor students' achievement (Chukwunta, 2024). Scholars have consistently emphasized the significant impact of teaching methods on students' academic performance.

The instructional methods employed by financial accounting teachers have been linked to poor retention and low achievement among students. This situation underscores the urgent need to explore alternative or active teaching approaches that foster deeper understanding and improved outcomes. In response, this study sought to examine the effects of constructivism, and meta-learning methods on the academic achievement and retention of financial accounting students in universities in Enugu State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to compare the effectiveness of constructivism and meta-learning on students' academic achievement and retention in financial accounting in universities in Enugu State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. determine the financial accounting mean achievement scores of years 4 students in the constructivism and meta-learning group in both pretest and posttest.
2. determine the financial accounting mean retention scores of years 4 students in the constructivism and meta-learning group in both pretest and posttest.
3. determine the mean achievement scores of male and female year 4 in the constructivism and meta-learning group in both pretest and posttest.
4. determine the financial accounting mean retention scores of male and female year 4 students in constructivism and meta-learning group.

Research questions

The following research questions guided this study.

1. What is the financial accounting mean achievement scores of year four students in the constructivism and meta-learning group in both pretest and posttest?
2. What is the financial accounting mean retention scores of year four students in the constructivism and meta-learning group in both pretest and posttest?
3. What is the mean retention achievement scores of male and female year four students in the constructivism and meta-learning group in both pretest and posttest?
4. What are the mean retention scores of male and female year four students in constructivism and meta-learning group in both pretest and posttest?

Research hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of year 4 financial accounting students taught using constructivism and meta-learning teaching method.
2. A significant difference does not exist in mean retention scores of year 4 financial accounting students taught using constructivism and meta-learning method.
3. There is no significant difference in mean achievement scores of male and female year 4 students taught financial accounting using constructivism and meta-learning method.
4. A significant difference does not exist in mean retention scores of male and female year 4 students taught financial accounting using constructivism and meta-learning method.

Methods

The study adopted a quasi-experimental design of non-equivalent control group design. Intact classes were used and there was no randomization of the research subjects into control and experimental groups. The study was conducted in universities in Enugu State. Enugu State, located in Nigeria's South-eastern region, is one of five states that make up the area. It comprises 17 Local Government Areas and is known for its strong presence in higher education. The state hosts six universities, made up of federal, state, and private institutions. Among them is the University of Nigeria, Nsukka, a prominent federal university. The state universities include Enugu State University of Science and Technology and Enugu State University of Medical and Applied Sciences, Igbo Eno. The private universities are Caritas University Enugu, Godfrey Okoye University in Ugwuomu Nike, Renaissance University Enugu, and Coal City University Enugu. Out of these institutions, only three currently offer Business Education with specialization in Accounting. These universities provide a broad spectrum of academic programmes, including various disciplines within accounting. Therefore, these institutions that offer accounting education were used as the population for the study.

The target population for the study comprised 123 year four accounting education students in the universities in Enugu State. Year four students were chosen because they possess a more advanced understanding of financial accounting. They have more experience and are better able to show how well the learning methods work. There was no sampling due to manageable size of the population. (One intact class was randomly sampled in each school and one of them was used for experimental and the other control). The first instrument was Financial Accounting Achievement Test I (FAAT I) otherwise known as pre-test was administered to students in order to determine their entry level. The second instrument was Financial Accounting Achievement Test II (FAAT II) otherwise known as Post-test was used to determine the academic achievement scores of students after treatment. Lastly, Financial Accounting Achievement Test III (FAAT III) a reshuffled of FAAT II was used to test retention ability of students after two weeks of treatment. The instruments for data collection were validated by three research experts, two from Department of Business Education and one expert in Measurement and Evaluation unit of Mathematics and Computer Education. They are from Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT). A

reliability coefficient of 0.80 was obtained using Kuder-Richardson formula 20 (K-R-20). The research questions were answered using mean with standard deviation. The hypotheses for the study were tested using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at 0.05 level of significance. A null hypothesis of no significant difference was upheld when the p-value reached a significance level that was greater than or equal to 0.05. On the other hand, the null hypothesis of no significant difference was not upheld when the p-value was less than 0.05. The scores were subjected to data analysis using statistical package for social sciences SPSS version 20 package.

Analysis of Research Questions

Research Question One

What is the financial accounting mean achievement scores of year four students in the constructivism and meta group in both pretest and posttest.

Table 1: Mean Academic Achievement Scores and Standard Deviation of Financial Accounting year four Students Exposed to Constructivism and Meta group in both Pretest and Posttest

Groups	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean gain
		X	SD1	X	SD2	
Constructivism	64	25.00	6.01	78.53	5.04	53.33
Meta-learning	59	34.11	7.02	74.02	7.21	39.91

Note: N= number of students, SD1 = standard deviation for pre-test, SD2 = standard deviation for post-test, \bar{x} = mean.

Data presented in Table 1 show that the pre-test, post-test achievement means scores of constructivist group are 25.00 and 78.53 with the standard deviation of 6.01 and 5.04. The mean gain is 53.53. The meta-learning group has a pre-test and post-test achievement mean scores of 34.11 and 74.02 with standard deviation of 7.02 and 7.21. The mean gain is 39.91. However, for each of the groups, the post-test achievement mean scores are higher than the pre-test achievement mean score with constructivist group having the higher mean gain. The result indicates that constructivist teaching method improved students' achievement better than meta-learning teaching method.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of year 4 financial accounting students taught using constructivism and meta learning method.

Table 2: Summary of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) between the Mean Academic Achievement Scores of Year 4 Financial Accounting Students taught with constructivism and those taught with Meta-learning Method

Source	Sum of squares	Df	Mean of squares	F-cal	Sig.	Remark
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Teaching method	432.015	1	432.015	11.212	.001	Rejected
Error	3122.152	121	32142.142			
Total	3554.167	120				

Data in Table 2 show that F ratio of 11.212 with 1 degree of freedom and p-value of .001 is obtained for teaching methods on students' academic achievement mean scores in Financial accounting. Since the p-value of .001 is less than 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is a significant difference between the academic achievement means scores of financial accounting students taught financial accounting using constructivist teaching method and those taught using meta-learning teaching method. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

Research Question Two

What is the financial accounting mean retention scores of year four students in the constructivism and meta group in both pretest and posttest?

Table 3: Mean Retention Scores and Standard Deviation of Financial Accounting year four Students Exposed to Constructivism and Meta group in both Pretest and Posttest

Groups	N	Pre-test		Delay Post-test		Mean gain
		X	SD1	X	SD2	
Constructivism	64	23.00	3.03	61.32	3.11	38.32
Meta-learning	59	22.11	3.12	54.02	4.33	31.91

Table 3 shows that the post-test and delay post test retention mean scores of constructivist group are 23.00 and 61.32 with standard deviation of 3.03 and 3.11 with a mean gain of 38.32. The meta-learning group has a post-test and delay post-test mean scores of 22.11 and 54.02 with standard deviation of 3.12 and 4.33 respectively. The mean gain of the meta-learning group is 31.91. This indicates that students taught with constructivist teaching method seem to have retained knowledge more than students taught with meta-learning method.

Hypothesis Two

A significant difference does not exist in mean retention scores of year 4 financial accounting students taught using constructivism and meta learning method

Table 4: Summary of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) between the Mean Retention Scores of Year 4 Financial Accounting Students taught with constructivism and those taught with Meta-learning Method

Source	Sum of squares	Df	Mean of squares	F-cal	Sig.	Remark
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Teaching method	522.113	1	522.113	10.212	.003	Rejected
Error	4133.152	121	4112.132			
Total	4655.264	120				

Table 4 shows that the F ratio of 10.212 with 1 degree of freedom and p-value of .003 is obtained for teaching methods on students' retention mean scores in financial accounting, since the p-value of .003 is less than 0.05 level of significance. This shows that significant difference exists between the retention mean scores of financial accounting students taught financial accounting using constructivist teaching method and those taught using meta-learning teaching method. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

Research Question Three

What is the mean retention achievement scores of male and female year four students in the constructivism and meta group in both pretest and posttest?

Table 5: Mean and Standard Deviation of Male and Female Year 4 Students' Academic Achievement Mean Score in Financial Accounting when Taught using Constructivism and Meta-learning Methods

Methods	Gender	N (123)	TIME 1 (Pre-test)		TIME 2 (Post-test)		Mg
			\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	
Constructivism	Male	31	17.11	2.40	49.23	3.35	32.12
	Female	33	15.21	2.12	42.19	4.16	26.98
Meta-learning	Male	28	16.22	2.18	49.13	4.45	32.91
	Female	31	13.11	2.32	42.19	4.22	29.08

Data in Table 5 reveal that males in the constructivist group have pre-test and post-test achievements mean scores of 17.11 and 49.23 with a standard deviation of 2.40 and 3.35. The mean gain is 32.12. The females have pre-test and post-test achievement mean scores of 15.21 and 42.19 with a standard deviation of 2.12 and 4.16. The mean gain of females is 26.98. Similarly, males in the meta-learning group have pre-test and post-test achievements mean scores of 16.22 and 49.13 with a standard deviation of 2.18 and 4.45. The mean gain is 32.91. The females have pre-test and post-test achievement mean scores of 13.11 and 42.19 with a standard deviation of 2.32 and 4.22. The mean gain of females is 29.08. This implies that in teaching financial accounting using constructivism and meta-learning, male students achieved more than their female counterparts.

Hypothesis Three

There is no significant difference in mean achievement scores of male and female year 4 students taught financial accounting using constructivism and meta learning method

Table 6: Summary of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) Difference between the Mean Academic Achievement Scores of Male and Female Financial Accounting Year 4 Students Exposed to Constructivism and Meta learning method

Source	Sum of squares	Df	Mean of squares	F-cal	Sig.	Remark
Gender	51.008	1	51.008	1.646	.001	Rejected
Error	1212.511	51	23.616			
Total	221421.00	56				

Table 6 shows that the F-ratio of 1.646 with 1 degree of freedom and p-value of .001 is obtained for gender on students' academic achievement mean scores when taught financial accounting using constructivist and meta-learning method. Since the p-value of .001 is less than 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is significant difference between the academic achievement mean scores of male and female financial accounting students taught financial accounting using constructivist teaching method. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

Research Question Four

What are the mean retention scores of male and female year four students in constructivism and meta group in both pretest and posttest?

Table 7: Mean and Standard Deviation of Male and Female Year 4 Students' Retention Scores in Financial Accounting when Taught using Constructivism and Meta-learning Methods

Methods	Gender	N (123)	TIME 1 (Pre-test)		TIME 2 (Post-test)		Mg
			\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	
Constructivism	Male	31	16.42	3.22	36.41	3.00	19.99
	Female	33	16.21	3.34	35.33	4.43	19.12
Meta-learning	Male	28	15.22	3.33	35.54	4.21	20.32
	Female	31	14.31	3.03	34.20	4.02	19.89

Data in Table 7 reveal that males in the constructivist group have pre-test and post-test achievements mean scores of 16.42 and 36.41 with a standard deviation of 3.22 and 3.00. The mean gain is 19.99. The females have pre-test and post-test achievement mean scores of 16.21 and 35.33 with a standard deviation of 3.34 and 4.43. The mean gain of females is 19.12. Similarly, males in the meta-learning group have pre-test and post-test achievements mean scores of 15.22 and 35.54 with a standard deviation of 3.33 and 4.21. The mean gain is 20.32. The females have pre-test and post-test achievement mean scores of 14.31 and 34.20 with a standard deviation of 3.03 and 4.02. The mean gain of females is 19.89. This implies that in teaching financial accounting using constructivism and meta-learning, male students retained more than female students.

Hypothesis Four

A significant difference does not exist in mean retention scores of male and female year 4 students taught financial accounting using constructivism and meta learning method.

Table 8: Summary of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) Difference between the Mean Retention Scores of Male and Female Financial Accounting Year 4 Students Exposed to Constructivism and Meta learning method

Source	Sum of squares	Df	Mean of squares	F-cal	Sig.	Remark
Gender	15.603	1	15.603	0.036	.002	Rejected
Error	1155.427	51	20.112			
Total	226321.00	56				

Table 8 shows that the F-ratio of .036 with 1 degree of freedom and p-value of .002 is obtained for gender on students' retention mean scores when taught financial accounting using constructivist teaching method, since the p-value of .002 is greater than 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is significant differences between the retention mean scores of male and female financial accounting students taught financial accounting using constructivist teaching method. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

Discussion of the Findings

The findings of the study are discussed below according to the research questions and hypotheses that guided the study. The results of the analysis of research question one revealed that constructivist teaching method improved financial accounting students' achievement better than meta-learning teaching method. The corresponding hypothesis revealed that there was a significant difference between the academic achievement means scores of financial accounting students taught financial accounting using constructivist teaching method and those taught using meta-learning teaching method. Constructivist method enhanced the students' performance and provides them with adaptive environment which enable them to learn what they need. This is so because, constructivist method engages, informs and allows for practice and creative use of material learned within each lesson. It is based on the principle that different individuals perceive and process experience in different preferred ways. These findings are in line with that of Umar and Kankia (2024) who reported Constructivist Learning Strategy have significantly enhanced students' performance in Chemistry among Secondary School Students in Katsina ZEQA, Nigeria. Similarly, Chukwunta (2024) reported that constructivism instructional method is effective for improving students' cognitive achievement. In the same vein, the result of this study concurs with the views of Bupo and Ibeneme (2024) who asserted that constructivism encourages students to learn more of the materials as their interest is kindled through motivation, team spirit and interaction with one another.

The evidence from analysis of research question two indicated that students taught with constructivist teaching method retained knowledge more than students taught with meta-learning method. Constructivist method appears to be activity-oriented method that tries to simulate students to action and significantly improve their retentions as reported. This finding is in line with that of Jimoh (2021) and Abdulsalam (2022) which reported significant retention after treatment with Constructivist Learning

Strategy. Similarly, from the finding, it was discovered that a significant difference existed between the retention mean scores of financial accounting students taught financial accounting using constructivist teaching method and those taught using meta-learning teaching method. This implies that both male and female students taught using constructivist and meta-learning methods performed at almost the different pace. This finding is contrary to that of Adaramola (2020) and Jimoh (2021), who discovered that Constructivist Learning Strategy is gender friendly. The findings corroborate with that of Abiogu, Ugwu and Ede (2020) which reported that male students had higher achievement scores than female counterpart when taught using constructivist learning strategy.

The result obtained from the study showed that male students exposed to constructivist teaching method had a mean gain of 32.12 while the female students had a mean gain of 26.98. On the other hand, male students exposed to meta-learning teaching method had a mean gain of 32.91 while female students had a mean gain of 29.08. This showed that male students exposed to constructivist teaching method had a higher mean gain than their female counterparts, but a lower mean gain than their female counterpart exposed to meta-learning teaching method. However, the findings further indicated that gender differences were significant since the p-value of .001 that is not greater than 0.05 level of significance. This implied that there was significant difference between the academic achievements mean scores of male and female financial accounting students taught financial accounting using constructivist teaching method and those taught using meta-learning teaching method. This is in line with the finding of Ilyas, Agus and Ahmad (2021) who reported that gender has significant effect on students' academic achievement. The findings of the study supported the findings of Uwakwe and Okeke (2023) who reported that male students performed better than females when taught mathematics using concept constructivism method. The finding is in disagreement with the findings of Bupo and Ibeneme (2024) which revealed that there was no significant difference in the achievement of male and female students in mathematics. The disagreement with the present study could be as a result of the fact that previous studies focused on using conventional methods in the teaching of financial accounting while the present study focused on using constructivist and meta-learning teaching method in teaching financial accounting. In addition, evidence from analysis of research question four revealed that male students exposed to constructivist teaching method had a mean gain of 19.99 while their female counterparts had a mean gain of 19.12. On the other hand, male students exposed to meta-learning teaching method had a mean gain of 20.32 while their female counterparts had a mean gain of 19.89. This showed that male students exposed to constructivist and meta-learning teaching method had a mean gain higher than their male counterparts. However, the findings indicated that gender differences were significant in students' retention mean scores, since the p-value of .002 was less than 0.05 level of significance. This implies that significant difference did exist between the retention mean scores of male and female students taught financial accounting using constructivist teaching method and those taught using meta-learning teaching method. The finding is in agreement with the finding of Eze, Ezenwafor and Obidile (2020) which

reported that gender has significant effect on students' retention. In the same view, the results of this study agree with the findings of Sushma (2020) which revealed there was significant differences in the retention mean scores of male and female students in business studies. This finding also supported the findings of Olowodun and Egonu (2023) that there was statistical significant difference in the mean retention scores of male and female students taught mathematics using constructivist learning strategy.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, which revealed that constructivist teaching method and meta-learning teaching method had significant effect on students' academic achievement in Financial Accounting, it was concluded that constructivist teaching method is more effective than meta-learning teaching method in improving academic achievement of Financial Accounting year 4 students in Financial Accounting. In addition, constructivist teaching method also happens to be more effective for enhancing retention ability of Financial Accounting students in Financial Accounting than meta-learning method because Financial Accounting students taught using constructivist method had a mean gain higher than the meta-learning method. Therefore, it was concluded that constructivist teaching is more effective for improving academic achievement and retention of Financial Accounting. Therefore, the efforts of school authorities, the teachers and other stakeholders should be geared towards the use of constructivist teaching method in teaching financial accounting.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Since the use of constructivist method enhance academic of students in financial accounting in universities, the lecturers in universities in Enugu State should adopt the use of this method for instructional delivery. This should come as the new policy of government to be integrated in the curriculum.
2. University lecturers of financial accounting should undergo in-service training for skill update in the use of modern and student-centred learning strategy such as constructivism. The in-service training should be sponsored by the lecturers or sponsored by the school in collaboration with ministry of education.
3. Seminars, workshops and conferences should be organized by States and Federal ministries of Education where lecturers and curriculum planners will be taught the application and use of various modern teaching techniques such as constructivist for effective teaching and learning of financial accounting.

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